

Research article

Impact of future climate scenarios on peatland and constructed wetland water quality: A mesocosm experiment within climate chambers

Shokoufeh Salimi^a, Miklas Scholz^{a,b,c,*}^a Division of Water Resources Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University, P.O. Box 118, 221 00, Lund, Sweden^b Department of Civil Engineering Science, School of Civil Engineering and the Built Environment, University of Johannesburg, Kingsway Campus, PO Box 524, Aukland Park, 2006, Johannesburg, South Africa^c Department of Town Planning, Engineering Networks and Systems, South Ural State University (National Research University), 76, Lenin prospekt, Chelyabinsk, 454080, Russian Federation

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Biogeochemistry
 Climate change
 Decomposition
 Regional climate model (RCM)
 Representative concentration pathway (RCP)
 Water quality

ABSTRACT

Water purification is one of the most essential services provided by wetlands. A lot of concerns regarding wetlands subjected to climate change relate to their susceptibility to hydrological change and the increase in temperature as a result of global warming. A warmer condition may accelerate the rate of decomposition and release of nutrients, which can be exported downstream and cause serious ecological challenges; e.g., eutrophication and acidification. The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of climate change on water quality in peatland and constructed wetland ecosystems subject to water level management. For this purpose, the authors simulated the current climate scenario base on the database from Malmö station (Scania, Sweden) for 2016 and 2017 as well as the future climate scenarios for the last 30 years of the century based on the Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) and different regional climate models (RCM) for a region wider than Scania County. For future climate change, the authors simulated low (RCP 2.6), moderate (RCP 4.5) and extreme (RCP 8.5) climate scenarios. All simulations were conducted within climate chambers for experimental peatland and constructed wetland mesocosms. Our results demonstrate that the effect of climate scenario is significantly different for peatlands and constructed wetlands (interactive effect) for the combined chemical variables. The warmest climate scenario RCP 8.5 is linked to a higher water purification function for constructed wetlands, but to a lower water purification function and a subsequent deterioration of peatland water qualities, even if subjected to water level management. The explanation for the different response of constructed wetlands and peatlands to climate change could be due to the fact that the substrate in the constructed wetland mesocosms and peatlands was different in terms of the organic matter quality and quantity. The utilization of nutrients by the plants and microbial community readily exceed the mineralization under a limited nutrient content (as we had in constructed wetland) when the temperature rises. However, concerning the extreme scenario RCP 8.5, the peatlands have shown a tendency to have reverse processes.

1. Introduction

Wetlands serve numerous critical functions in the landscape. Water purification is one of the most important wetland services that has environmental benefits. Reduction and removal of nutrients and pollutants are accomplished through physical and biochemical processes such as microbial decomposition, assimilation, filtration, precipitation, sedimentation and adsorption (Henrichs et al., 2007; Scholz and Hedmark, 2010). Wetlands have a high rate of productivity. This means that nutrients can be greatly absorbed and stored in the plant biomass.

However, the prevalent-waterlogged environment of wetlands, which creates an anoxic state, does not allow the same rate of decomposition to occur and this unbalanced rate of production and decomposition results in a net accumulation of organic matter in wetland soils (Laiho, 2006).

A lot of concerns regarding wetland ecosystems subject to climate change are due to their susceptibility to hydrological change and temperature rise (Burkett and Kusler, 2000). A warmer condition leads to a higher degree of evapotranspiration, which can trigger an aerobic environment. This can accelerate the rate of decomposition and release of nutrients, which can be exported downstream and cause serious

* Corresponding author. Division of Water Resources Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University, P.O. Box 118, 221 00, Lund, Sweden.

E-mail addresses: shokoufeh.salimi@tvrl.lth.se (S. Salimi), miklas.scholz@tvrl.lth.se (M. Scholz).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112459>

Received 6 October 2020; Received in revised form 11 March 2021; Accepted 19 March 2021

Available online 31 March 2021

0301-4797/© 2021 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

ecological problems; e.g., eutrophication (Karczmarczyk et al., 2016; Zak et al., 2017) and acidification (Pagano et al., 2014).

Research on the response of wetland water quality to future climate scenarios is very rare (Yan and Xu, 2014). However, a number of experimental studies have investigated the impact of the two main factors temperature and hydrology on wetland nutrient dynamics (Moore et al., 1998; Bridgman et al., 1999; Pastor et al., 2003; Macrae et al., 2013). The magnitude of water level decline may determine the rates of nutrient mineralization as well as microbial and plant assimilation. For example, Macrae et al. (2013) stated that a 20 cm lower water table would stimulate the microbial and plant activity to immobilize nutrients, while this decline was not sufficient for nutrient release.

Studies on DOC release from peatlands have been receiving increased attention as it has a significant impact on the aquatic system (Karlsson et al., 2009; Erlandsson et al., 2010). Research suggests that DOC exports may increase (Clair et al., 1999) or decrease (Moore et al., 1998; Pastor et al., 2003) depending on hydrological conditions. For example, Freeman et al. (2001) show findings for bogs in the United Kingdom, demonstrating that both DOC concentration and export increased in parallel with the observed warming trend over the past 20 years. Pastor et al. (2003) experimentally warmed and controlled water tables for mesocosms collected from a fen (dominant sedge) and a bog (dominant sphagnum moss) in northern Minnesota, USA. Their findings showed a decrease in DOC exports due to reduced discharge in both fen and bog mesocosms, despite warmer conditions and higher DOC concentrations.

The response of the different types of wetlands to warmer climate may be different due to their various characteristics. Bridgman et al. (1998) collected samples from bogs (vegetated with black spruce, *Sphagnum* spp., and ericaceous shrubs), poor (acid) and intermediate fens (both of which were dominated by sedge), forested swamps (Cedar and Tamarack) and Meadowlands (with dominant vegetation of Canada blue joint, wool grass, and sedge) for carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorous mineralization study on ombrotrophic-minerotrophic gradients in northern Minnesota, USA. Their findings showed that mineralization of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorous differed significantly among wetland types, aeration status (aerobic vs. anaerobic) and their interaction term. Moreover, they noted that while ombrotrophic peatland have low total soil nitrogen and phosphorous compared to minerotrophic, they have a rapid turnover particularly under aerobic conditions. The rate of nutrients release between different types of wetland could be different due to various soil compositions (Koerselman et al., 1993) and bulk density of soil (Bridgman et al., 1998).

Temperature sensitivity of decomposition in the oxic layer of the peat profile increases with depth, age and recalcitrance (Biasi et al., 2005; Conant et al., 2008; Hartley and Ineson, 2008). Hiltunen et al. (2013) examined the decomposability and temperature sensitivity of the different layers of the *Sphagnum* peat profile extracted from the raised bog in Central Finland. They indicated that the decomposition of the recalcitrant compounds in the oxic layer is more temperature sensitive than the labile compounds.

The response of different nutrients to the warmer climate may be completely different. Nadelhoffer et al. (1991) conducted an experiment to investigate the effects of temperature, soil moisture and fertilizer on different soil cores (from tussock, intertussock, sedge and heath) extracted from Alaskan tundra. The response of soil cores to treatment at two temperatures of 7 or 15 °C and under saturated or well-drained conditions showed that nitrogen and phosphorous mineralization is more temperature-dependent than carbon.

Breeuwer et al. (2008) conducted two experiments to analyze the decomposability of three types of organic matter including recalcitrant (*Sphagnum fuscum*), decomposable (*Sphagnum balticum*) and *Eriophorum vaginatum* litter. The samples originated from four bogs along a gradient from northern Sweden to north-eastern Germany, where temperatures increased from north to south. Their results indicated that the release of nitrogen did not differ with temperature increase for both *Sphagnum* and

vascular plants litter. They stated that it is likely that intrinsic litter composition is a more determinant factor in decomposability than the temperature (Limpens and Berendse, 2003; Bragazza et al., 2007).

It is unclear how different climate conditions affect water purification efficiency in constructed wetlands. Many biogeochemical reactions accelerate with higher temperatures. The reaction of microbial enzymes accelerates to a certain degree with higher temperature; i.e. each microbial enzyme has an optimum temperature where it can function most effectively. On the other hand, this ideal temperature varies, because other parameters such as hydraulic loading, substrate quality and vegetation interactively can also influence the microbial activity within a constructed wetland (Fenoy et al., 2016).

Higher temperatures can be presumed to increase the microbial growth that enhances the removal of nutrients (Kadlec, 2003; Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2006; Paredes et al., 2007; Zhou et al., 2017). In addition, a longer growing season increases nutrient uptake in constructed wetlands (Kadlec and Wallace, 2009; Kelvin and Tole, 2011).

Zhou et al. (2017) found that temperature has a major impact on the removal function of constructed wetlands. They suggested that with a decrease in temperature, the removal percentages of ammonium, nitrate, total nitrogen and total phosphorus will decline. However, Mæhlum and Jenssen. (2003) could not find substantial differences in the removal efficiency of Norwegian constructed wetlands between cold (<4 °C) and warm (>11 °C) conditions for the parameters TP, TN, COD, BOD and TSS. Akrotos and Tsihrintzis (2007) have stated that the bacteria and plants responsible for nitrogen removal at low temperatures would not function as efficiently as at high ones. The quality of the substrate has been shown to have a significant effect that it can conceal the influence of temperature on decomposition (Kadlec and Reddy, 2001).

As the literature indicates, there is no certainty how higher temperature can affect the wetland biogeochemistry (Gholz et al., 2000; Parton et al., 2007; Fenoy et al., 2016). This is due to the fact that both wetland ecosystem and climate change are dynamic and complex. Moreover, the processes in wetlands involve the interplay of opposite effects and nuanced positive and negative feedback (Davidson and Janssens, 2006; Plante et al., 2010; Schlesinger and Bernhardt, 2013), which require further research.

The aim of this study is to assess the effect of climate change on water quality of wetlands (peatland and constructed wetland) under water level management. The research also evaluates whether the response of peatlands and constructed wetlands to climate change is different. For this purpose, the authors have benefited from a unique mesocosm experiment within advanced climate chambers. They simulated dynamic climate change scenarios (simulation of various climate variables, temperature, precipitation, relative humidity and radiation simultaneously) based on future climate representative carbon pathways (RCP) scenarios with a high precision. In addition, the climate chamber mesocosm experiment allows for the simulation of small changes between climate scenarios. Researchers will then have the opportunity to recognize the subtle changes in response (physicochemical variables) of wetland systems that may otherwise be masked in field experiments due to the complexity of the natural system and the interaction of many different variables beyond the control of the assessor (Salimi et al., 2021). The designed mesocosm experiment in this study enabled the team to monitor the changes in water quality of two different types of wetlands (peatland and constructed wetland) simultaneously. Moreover, this design helped the researchers to manage the water level to be able to highlight the effect of small changes in temperature as the key climate variable that could alter the water purification function of the wetland.

In order to achieve the aim of the study, the authors defined specific objectives: (a) to determine the effect of different climate scenarios on wetland outflow water quality by measuring physicochemical parameters in peatland (bog) and constructed wetland mesocosms; and (b) to compare the response of peatlands and constructed wetlands under

different climate scenarios when the hydrology is not a stress factor in these two ecosystems.

2. Methodology

2.1. Climate scenario creation

2.1.1. Data collection

Data of ten different regional climate models (RCM) were obtained from the Rossby Centre of the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) as shown in the electronic supplementary material (Table ESM1). The data for the RCM were generated for different future climate scenarios. Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) were released by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (AR5; IPCC, 2007).

In this project, the data of the RCM were collected for the RCP 2.6, 4.5 and 8.5 (Table ESM1) to simulate low, moderate and extreme future climate change scenarios. The data were collected for a domain wider than Scania County located in southern Sweden. The domain is located between longitudes 11 (west) and 14 (east), and between latitudes 55 (north) and 57 (south).

The climate variables temperature, humidity, radiation and precipitation were used to simulate different climate scenarios within the climate chambers (Fig. 2). Hourly data of these variables for the current climate scenario (2016 and 2017 data from Malmö A station) were obtained from SMHI (<http://opendata-download-metobs.smhi.se/explore/>). There were five RCM data series available at SMHI for the RCP 2.6 and ten RCM series for the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5.

2.1.2. Delta change approach

The delta change method (Hay et al., 2000) was used to create future climate scenarios for the experiment. For this purpose, the difference between the output of the RCM for the last 30 years of the century (2069–2098) and the historical data of the same models for the same number of years (1976–2005) was calculated.

The monthly average was computed for each variable and for each model, and then the average of 30 years for both historical and RCM data was calculated separately. Moreover, the average of the available models for each RCP was estimated. The monthly delta change values were computed by subtracting the average of the historical data from the average of the RCM data.

2.2. Climate chambers

In order to simulate the climate scenarios, the authors used four climate chambers KK 750 (Pol-Eko-Aparatura Wodzisław Śląski, Poland; <https://www.pol-eko.com.pl/model/climatic-chambers-kk/climatic-chamber-kk-750/>). The climate chambers were equipped with a phytotron system, which controls temperature and humidity. In addition, each climate chamber was equipped with an 840 (daylight) fluorescent lamp to simulate day and night. There is also an air flap and a ventilator to provide stable conditions for air extraction and circulation. The climate chamber regulates both the intensity and duration of the illumination. Moreover, the climate chambers are equipped with an ultrasonic humidifier, which requires deionized water to provide the set humidity in the climate chambers. The climate chambers are remotely programmable allowing the user to regulate the temperature and relative humidity, as well as radiation at a 3-h resolution. Precipitation simulation was conducted manually on a weekly basis (Fig. 1).

2.3. Experimental design

The experiment was started on July 1, 2017 and is still running. Two different systems (peatland and constructed wetland) were placed in four different climate chambers (Fig. 1). The climate scenarios were simulated in the climate chambers as follows: current climate (climate chamber 1), RCP 2.6 (climate chamber 2), RCP 4.5 (climate chamber 3) and RCP 8.5 (climate chamber 4) (Fig. 2). Each ecosystem includes four replicates; i.e. there are 8 mesocosms in each climate chamber and a total of 32 mesocosms in the experiment (Fig. 2).

Each mesocosm system was established in a 14-L glass tank (300 mm width; 220 mm depth; 240 mm height) made from soda-lime glass. Top peatland samples (approximately 20–22 cm peat and 2–6 cm *Sphagnum* moss (heights of any shrubs and graminoids are not included)) were collected from an ombrotrophic bog called Fäjemyr, which is situated in the province of Scania in southern Sweden (latitude of 56°15'N, longitude of 13°33'E and altitude of 140 m).

The constructed wetland tanks were filled with a layer of approximately 8 cm of pea gravel (4–8 mm), followed by a 14-cm layer of washed sand (0–4 mm). All constructed wetland mesocosms were planted with the perennial aquatic plant *Myosotis scorpioides* L. (water forget-me-not) at a density of 10 plants per mesocosm.

Fig. 1. Different ecosystem mesocosms (peatland (P) and constructed wetland (CW)) within climate chambers simulating different climate variables. WL, water level.

Fig. 2. Overview of the experimental design (RCP, representative concentration pathway; P, peatland; CW, constructed wetland).

2.4. Water level management

Precipitation was simulated for the mesocosms in the climate chambers on a weekly basis and based on the precipitation data obtained from the climate scenario values. Rainwater (inflow) was added manually to the mesocosms (Fig. 1). However, in the first year of the project, the water level in the mesocosms was managed to examine the effect of the scenarios in a situation where they were not stressed with extreme events such as flood or drought.

The mesocosms were managed to keep the water level between 10 (minimum water level) and 18 cm (maximum water level) above the bottom of the tank (Fig. 1). The adjustment of the water level was performed by adding water (inflow to the wetlands) obtained from the sustainable flood retention basin called Lake Lake (Sjön Sjön in Swedish; located on the campus of the Faculty of Engineering at Lund University), when the water level was lower than 10 cm after the addition of rainwater or by removing (a) excess rainwater; (b) run-off defined as the overflow water when the capacity of the mesocosm has been exceeded; and (c) management defined as the amount of water that has to be removed to lower the water level to a height between 10 and 18 cm (Fig. 1). Water was removed from the vertical stand pipe located in the center of each mesocosm. This soil water represents the outflow, and was abstracted via syringe suction. In comparable natural wetlands, this excess water may be periodically drained out of the wetland through ditches or pipes to subsequently enter surrounding waterbodies.

2.5. Analysis of physicochemical parameters

The key physicochemical parameters were selected to understand how the wetlands mesocosms water quality might change under different climate scenarios over time. The concentrations of the chemical variables were monitored for the first six months (the data are not displayed because they are bulky) to determine which variables might exceed the standard levels according to the regulations from European

Economic Community. EU framework Directives 1991/271/EEC proposed quality standards for surface fresh water, which were used in this study for comparison. The ranges of the chemical variables were compared to the standard levels and the variables that were classified into the higher range groups were chosen to continue to be measured in this study. Based on this chemical concentration assessment, our measurements were limited to a few numbers of nutrients including dissolved organic carbon (DOC), ammonium, total phosphorus as well as chemical oxygen demand (COD) and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD). Moreover, physical water quality parameters such as dissolved oxygen (DO), total suspended solids (TSS) and, electric conductivity (EC) were measured in this study.

The dissolved organic carbon (DOC), which is the dissolved fraction of total organic carbon (TOC) and has a smaller molecular weight than the dissolved fraction can pass through the microbial cell membranes and be metabolized more readily. Dissolved organic carbon was analyzed using the TOC analyzer TOC-V CPH-TNM-1 (Shimadzu). Bioavailability of organic matter can be quantified by measuring the variable biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) defined as the amount of oxygen required by the microorganisms to decompose the organic compounds in a specified time (e.g., for five days which is expressed as BOD₅). The 5-day biological oxygen demand (BOD) was measured using the OxiTop Control System OC 110® (WTW, Germany). While BOD provide us with information about the biodegradability of organic matter in the wetland substrate, another variable, chemical oxygen demand (COD), enables us to understand how much organic and inorganic matter in the wetland medium can be chemically oxidized, thus, COD is usually higher than BOD (Scholz, 2016). The chemical oxygen demand (COD) of the mesocosm samples was analyzed with the Hach test kits LCK-314, 514, 614 and 1414 using the dichromate method according to ISO 6060-1989 and DIN 38409-H41-H44, and were measured by spectrophotometer (DR 3900 Hach Lange, Germany).

Decomposition generally refers to carbon losses of organic matter (the relevant variables mentioned above), while mineralization generally refers to transformations of two key nutrients, nitrogen and phosphorus which are essential for plant growth and can be assimilated mainly through plant photosynthesis. However, from a microbial point of view, mineralization and decomposition are strongly interrelated and can be considered to be the same process (Bayley et al., 2005). Total phosphorus (TP) was analyzed using the inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) Optima 8300 (Perkin Elmer ELAN 6100, Perkin Elmer Inc., Waltham, Mass), in accordance with the USEPA method 200.7 (USEPA, 1994). Furthermore, ammonium-nitrogen (NH₄-N) was monitored in this study, determined with flow injection analysis FIA using a FIAstar 5000 Analyzer (Foss Tecator, Höganäs, Sweden) according to ISO 11732:2005 and ISO 11732, respectively.

Wetland is supposed to improve the physical characteristics of the water. One of the key physical variable, dissolved oxygen, were measured in order to quantify the aerobic/anaerobic state of the wetland. Higher temperature with climate change lowers the water level and introduces more oxygen to the wetland profile, which stimulates the aerobic decomposition that occurs at a faster rate than anaerobic decomposition. Dissolved oxygen (DO) was measured directly from the mesocosms outflow pipe, along with other variables each month.

Amount of the filterable solids present in a sample can be determined by measuring a physical variable called total suspended solid (TSS). Climate change is likely to result in more frequent and intense floods, which could increase the runoff and erosion of wetland soils that might increase the TSS. Moreover, the decomposition of organic matter as a result of the warmer climate might cause the organic particles to break down and increase the suspended solids in the water column (Lane et al., 2007). Total suspended solids (TSS) were measured using Lovibond MD 100 (VWR, Germany). Electrical conductivity is the ability of water samples to conduct an electric current. Higher conductivity value indicates that there is high amount of nutrients, salts or impurities in the

water. The electric conductivity (EC) was determined with the Conductivity Meter CO 310 (VWR, Germany).

It is important to note that there is an interrelationship between most of the variables mentioned above. For example, high levels of total suspended solids will increase water temperatures and decrease dissolved oxygen (DO) levels. The lower water level in wetlands introduces more oxygen to the wetland soil profile, which causes oxidation of organic matter, leading to a faster decomposition of organic matter. All the variables DOC, COD and BOD are interrelated to each other. They all were measured in this study to have a comprehensive view on dynamic of changes.

2.6. Data analysis

A two-way repeated-measures multivariate analysis of variance (RM-MANOVA) was used to test the effect of main factors wetland type, climate scenario and their interactions on physicochemical parameter changes over time. The normality of data was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Data were normalized using the z-score normalization method to meet the pre-condition of RM-MANOVA. Moreover, the physicochemical parameters were divided into chemical and physical parameters to obtain an adequate sample size relative to the number of dependent variables. Wilk's Lambda was used in RM-MANOVA to assess the significance of the main factors. Effect sizes of the RM-MANOVA were examined using partial eta squared (η_p^2). In order to determine pairwise differences, the Bonferroni adjustment test (Sokal

and Rohlf, 1995) was performed. Significance levels were set at $p < 0.05$ for all tests. All data analyses were conducted using software IBM SPSS Statistics 25.0 as well as Minitab 19.

3. Results

3.1. Climate scenario simulation

Fig. 3 shows the monthly average of the climate variables for different climate scenarios, which have been used for the simulation. Temperature, precipitation (Fig. 3b) and relative humidity (Fig. 3a) had an increasing trend from the coldest scenario (current climate) to the warmest scenario (RCP 8.5). However, radiation had a decreasing trend (Fig. 3a).

The difference between the annual average temperature of the future climate scenarios RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5, RCP 8.5 and the current climate (control scenario) was 1.8 ± 0.52 , 2 ± 0.43 and 3.2 ± 0.75 °C, respectively. The RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5, RCP 8.5 have experienced 1.02 ± 0.082 , 1.09 ± 0.072 and 1.15 ± 0.137 times higher annual average precipitation relative to the current scenarios respectively. Radiation in the RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5, RCP 8.5 had an annual average ratio of 0.98 ± 0.033 , 0.95 ± 0.028 and 0.94 ± 0.033 to the current climate, respectively.

The difference between the relative humidity of the scenarios was relatively small with the ratios of 1.003 ± 0.0113 , 1.007 ± 0.0062 and 1.009 ± 0.0108 for RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 compared to the current climate scenario, respectively. The average of the water levels

Fig. 3. Monthly average values of different climate variables: (a) radiation and relative humidity; and (b) temperature and precipitation simulated for four different climate scenarios within climate chambers. The data for the current climate originate from the Malmö meteorological station for the years 2016 and 2017). The future climate scenario data are the values from the created climate scenarios for the last 30 years of the 21st century for different RCP.

for the current climate, RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios was 12.4 ± 2.10 , 12.0 ± 2.43 , 13.3 ± 2.24 and 13.4 ± 2.48 over the course of the experiment. There were not significant ($p > 0.05$) differences between the water level of the mesocosms under different climate scenarios.

3.2. Effect of climate scenarios, wetland type and their interactions on chemical variables

The results of the repeated measured multivariate analysis of variance showed that there was no statistically significant effect of climate scenario on the combined chemical variables (TP, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, DOC, COD and BOD) ($p = 0.060$, Wilks' Lambda = 0.321, $\eta_p^2 = 0.315$). However, the effect of climate scenario was found to be significant for $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and DOC (Table 1). The effect of wetland type on the combined chemical variables was significant, ($p < 0.001$, Wilks' Lambda = 0.056, $\eta_p^2 = 0.944$). In addition, this effect was statistically significant for each chemical variable (Table 1). The interactive effect of climate scenario and wetland type on the combined chemical variables was found to be significant ($p = 0.009$, Wilks' Lambda = 0.235, $\eta_p^2 = 0.383$). This interactive effect was statistically significant for TP, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and COD (Table 1). The pairwise comparison showed that the peatland mesocosm under RCP 8.5 had a significantly higher mean DOC compared to the ones under RCP 2.6 and RCP 4.5, and this difference was evident over the year (Fig. 5e). The authors found the lowest mean DOC under RCP 2.6 (Fig. 4e) and a constant decreasing trend over the year for this climate scenario (Fig. 5e). In contrast, RCP 8.5 had the highest mean DOC (Fig. 4e). Similar findings were observed for $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$; i.e. peatland mesocosms under RCP 8.5 had a significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher mean $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ compared to those under RCP 2.6 and RCP 4.5 (Fig. 4c). The authors found no significant ($p > 0.05$) differences between the mean values of other physiochemical variables for peatland mesocosms for different climate scenarios. However, the peatland mesocosm under RCP 8.5 had the highest mean TP, COD and BOD among the other climate scenarios (Fig. 4a,g,h). After scenario RCP 8.5, the current climate scenario experienced the highest mean $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, DOC and COD (Fig. 4c,e,g). The lowest mean $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and DOC was measured for the RCP 2.6 scenario (Fig. 4c,e). During the growing season (May to September), BOD showed an increasing trend from the coldest scenario to the warmest one (Fig. 5h).

Regarding the constructed wetland, the pairwise comparison between the climate scenarios showed that the mean TP under the current climate is significantly higher than for all future climate scenarios (Fig. 4a). Moreover, the mean COD under the current climate was significantly higher than RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 (Fig. 4g). In addition, the mean BOD under RCP 8.5 was significantly lower than the current climate and RCP 2.6 (Fig. 4h). The greatest mean TP, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and COD concentrations for the constructed wetlands (Fig. 4a,c,g) were found for the current climate scenario. The highest mean TP and COD in the

constructed wetland mesocosms under the current climate scenario was almost continuously recorded (Fig. 6a,g). The constructed wetland mesocosms under RCP 8.5 showed the lowest mean BOD (Fig. 4h) and this was evident over time (Fig. 6h). The pairwise comparison between the peatland and constructed wetland showed a significant difference between these two types of wetlands under each climate scenario for all chemical variables except for TP under the current climate scenario (Fig. 4a).

3.3. Effect of climate scenario, wetland type and their interaction on physical variables

There was a statistically significant effect of climate scenario on the combined physical variables (DO, TSS and conductivity) ($p = 0.001$, Wilks' Lambda = 0.235, $\eta_p^2 = 0.383$). Significant effects of climate scenario have been found for DO and TSS (Table 1). The effect of wetland type on the combined physical variables was significant as well ($p < 0.001$, Wilks' Lambda = 0.318, $\eta_p^2 = 0.682$). However, the interactive effect of climate scenario and wetland type on the combined physical variables was not significant ($p = 0.798$, Wilks' Lambda = 0.746, $\eta_p^2 = 0.093$).

Regarding peatlands, there was no significant difference between different climate scenarios in terms of physical variables ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 4). However, the pairwise comparison showed a significant difference between the mean DO in constructed wetland mesocosms under RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 ($p < 0.05$) as shown in Fig. 4f. Moreover, the mean TSS in constructed wetland mesocosms under RCP 2.6 was significantly higher than those under the current climate scenario ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4d).

The pairwise comparison between the peatland and constructed wetland showed that the mean DO and conductivity of peatlands and constructed wetlands under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 were significantly different (Fig. 4g). However, the mean TSS of peatlands and constructed wetlands was significantly different for the current climate scenario and RCP 2.6 (Fig. 4d).

4. Discussion

There was a tendency of higher concentration of chemical variables in the peatland mesocosms under the climate scenario RCP 8.5, while the constructed wetland mesocosms under the current climate scenario showed a higher tendency of chemical variables. Moreover, the interactive effect of climate change and wetland type was found to be statistically different for the combined chemical variables indicating that the effect of different climate scenario on chemical variables is not similar for the peatland and constructed wetland; i.e. significantly different for TP, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and COD.

It seems that higher temperatures have impaired the quality of peatland mesocosms outflow under scenario RCP 8.5. However, the

Table 1

Results of a two-way repeated measured multivariate analysis of variance showing the effects of the main factors climate scenario, wetland type and their interactions with physiochemical variables.

Factor	Climate scenario				Wetland type				Climate scenario*Wetland type			
	df	F	p	η_p^2	df	F	P	η_p^2	df	F	p	η_p^2
TP	3	2.00	0.143	0.21	1	27.52	<0.001	0.54	3	5.09	0.008	0.40
$\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$	3	4.80	0.010	0.38	1	183.27	<0.001	0.89	3	3.89	0.022	0.34
DOC	3	3.72	0.026	0.33	1	120.47	<0.001	0.84	3	1.84	0.168	0.19
COD	3	2.97	0.053	0.28	1	147.38	<0.001	0.87	3	5.69	0.005	0.43
BOD	3	1.90	0.158	0.20	1	163.96	<0.001	0.88	3	2.83	0.061	0.27
DO	3	6.70	0.003	0.51	1	13.50	0.002	0.42	3	0.63	0.603	0.09
TSS	3	4.66	0.013	0.42	1	13.76	0.001	0.42	3	0.99	0.419	0.14
Cond	3	0.81	0.503	0.11	1	14.04	0.001	0.42	3	0.09	0.966	0.01

BOD, biochemical oxygen demand (mg/l); COD, chemical oxygen demand (mg/l); Cond, electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$); DO, dissolved oxygen (mg/l); DOC, dissolved oxygen demand (mg/l); $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, ammonium-nitrogen (mg/l); TP, total phosphorous (mg/l); TSS, total suspended solid (mg/l).

Note: Partial Eta Squared (η_p^2) denotes the effect size. Bold p-values indicate statistical significance at $p < 0.05$.

Fig. 4. Box plots for (a) total phosphorus (TP); (b) conductivity; (c) ammonium-nitrogen (N); (d) total suspended solids (TSS); (e) dissolved organic carbon (DOC); (f) dissolved oxygen (DO); (g) chemical oxygen demand (COD); and (h) biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) for constructed wetlands and peatlands concerning four different climate scenarios; current climate (CC), RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5. Note: The box represents median and interquartile range. The whiskers represent the ranges for the bottom 25% and the top 25% of the data values. The mean is displayed as a plus sign inside a circle. Significant differences between constructed wetlands and peatlands for each climate scenario have been indicated by an asterisk. Significant differences between climate scenarios have been shown with lower case letters for constructed wetlands and upper case letters for peatlands. Means that share the same letter(s) are not significantly different from each other. The significance test is based on the pairwise comparison, Bonferroni adjusted significance tests, followed by two-way repeated-measures multivariate analysis of variance (RM-MANOVA). The mean difference is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Fig. 5. The trends for (a) total phosphorus (TP); (b) conductivity; (c) ammonium-nitrogen (N); (d) total suspended solids (TSS); (e) dissolved organic carbon (DOC); (f) dissolved oxygen (DO); (g) chemical oxygen demand (COD); and (h) biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) under different climate scenarios for the peatland mesocosms.

adverse effects of elevated temperatures in other future climate scenarios have not been observed. This might be due to the fact that a mild increase in temperature not only increase the decomposition rate, but also the rate of nutrient assimilation through the process of plant growth and microbial biomass build-up. We speculate that the highest temperature under the RCP 8.5 scenario led to a higher rate of organic matter decomposition and nutrient production exceeding nutrient consumption (assimilation) resulting in higher concentrations of all nutrient-related variables (TP, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and DOC) as well as COD and BOD in peatland mesocosm outflows under the RCP 8.5 scenario.

Other studies showed that the more recalcitrant carbon compounds, the more temperature-sensitive the system was (Hardie et al., 2011; Hilsavuori et al., 2013; Bader et al., 2018). The authors understand that the RCP 8.5 scenario having the highest temperature not only resulted in the production of the labile compounds being released from the readily decomposable litters on the top part of the mesocosms, but also could reach to the peat with more refractory compounds. Therefore, the impact of the higher temperature on the RCP 8.5 might result in simultaneous increases in both recalcitrant and labile compounds (Kane et al., 2014; Dieleman et al., 2016).

Studies have shown that an increase in temperature promotes nitrogen mineralization in peatland (Hobbie, 1996; Rustad et al., 2001).

Their results support our findings for scenario RCP 8.5, where the peatland mesocosms experienced a higher concentration of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, indicating a higher rate of decomposition. The results of some other studies (Verhoeven et al., 1990; Breeuwer et al., 2008) on nitrogen do not support our results as they could not find a higher concentration of nitrogen with warmer conditions in the *Sphagnum* and *E. vaginatum* dominated peatlands.

The studies documented that dependent to the dominance of vegetation in peatlands, the nutrient dynamics might change. A warmer condition promotes vascular vegetation abundance, dominating over moss coverage (Munir, 2015; Smith et al., 2017). Munir et al. (2017) investigated the dynamics of peatland nitrogen and phosphorus in a continental wooded-bog (*Sphagnum* mosses dominant interspersed with sparse shrubs) in Alberta, Canada. They reported that the newly available soil nitrogen pool is more accessible to vascular plants than to mosses.

The authors have observed a slight expansion of vascular plants in the peatland mesocosms under all future climate scenarios. Therefore, the team assumes that this consumption of nitrogen by the vascular plants might have happened in the mesocosms under all future climate scenarios and exceeding the nitrogen release in the climate scenarios, RCP2.6 and RCP 4.5, but not in the RCP 8.5 scenario, which showed a

Fig. 6. The trends for (a) total phosphorus (TP); (b) conductivity; (c) ammonium-nitrogen (N); (d) total suspended solids (TSS); (e) dissolved organic carbon (DOC); (f) dissolved oxygen (DO); (g) chemical oxygen demand (COD); and (h) biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) under different climate scenarios for the constructed wetland mesocosms.

higher concentration of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$. Literature indicate that production of DOC is the result of microbial enzymatic activity and physical leaching of organic matter (Moore and Dalva, 1997). Higher temperatures in RCP 8.5 accompanied by adequate water availability led to higher rates of DOC leaching from the peatland mesocosms in this scenario relative to the other scenarios.

Moreover, a higher amount of DOC in peatland mesocosms during spring compared to summer in all scenarios indicates an important function of leaching for net DOC production. Hence, in the RCP 8.5 scenario, the impact of higher precipitation and temperature interaction might cause higher degree of decomposition and leaching triggering higher net production of DOC in peatlands (Bridgham et al., 1999; Pastor et al., 2003).

Numerous studies have reported higher concentrations of DOC with a warmer climate (Freeman et al., 2001; Evans et al., 2005; Höll et al., 2009; Hribljan et al., 2014; Kane et al., 2014), which supports our findings. However, our results contrast with Preston et al. (2011), who indicate that temperature had no effect on DOC production in their peat microcosm (collected from a Coniferous-Sphagnum swamp in central Ontario peatland), regardless of moisture treatment.

Comparing the magnitude of the increase in BOD and COD in

peatland mesocosms under the RCP 8.5 scenario relative to other climate scenarios during the summer, it can be inferred that the adverse impact of RCP 8.5 on the decomposition of organic matter and the production of labile organic matter, are more highlighted during the warm season. Moreover, the higher rate of increase in total phosphorus was also seen for peatland mesocosms under RCP 8.5. Interestingly during the summer, the increasing trend in BOD and COD in peatland mesocosms between the climate scenarios follows the increasing trend for temperature between climate scenarios (Fig. 5). This implies the dominant impact of temperature on water quality.

Considering that the initial baseline of nutrients in peatland mesocosms under RCP 2.6 and RCP 4.5 were fairly close, they could be easily compared. There seems to be an increasing pattern in the concentration of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, DOC, BOD and COD under RCP 4.5 compared to RCP 2.6 during the summer when the temperature difference between RCP 4.5 and RCP 2.6 reaches a maximum of 0.5 °C all-year around. This difference does not exceed 0.1 °C during spring. Hence, the difference between the concentrations of nutrients is also low. This emphasizes the importance of the temperature on water quality change, even at a very small scale between 0 and 0.5 °C.

Surprisingly, the constructed wetland mesocosms under the RCP 8.5

scenario with the highest temperature did not show impaired water quality; instead the mesocosms under the current climate with the coldest condition have recorded the lowest water quality showing the highest mean TP, NH₄, DOC, COD and conductivity values.

The lowest mean BOD and the second lowest mean COD in the constructed wetlands under RCP 8.5 indicate a low concentration of pollutants in this scenario. Enhanced biochemical activity with higher temperature can be the key factor causing a higher rate of pollution removal under RCP 8.5. These findings confirm the influence of temperature on biochemical activity improving the quality of the constructed wetland outflow. The effect of higher temperature on the constructed wetland water purification function has already been indicated (Kadlec, 2003; Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2006; Paredes et al., 2007; Zhou et al., 2017). Our results for constructed wetlands are in agreement with the findings recorded by Akratos and Tsihrintzis (2007), which noted that the removal efficiency for organic matter, nitrogen and orthophosphate would be increased, if the temperature reaches above 15 °C. However, our results contradict the findings recorded by Züst and Schönborn (2003), which showed no influence of wastewater temperature on the removal efficiency of COD in constructed wetlands.

In general, the authors discovered a tendency of ammonium reduction in constructed wetland mesocosms under future climate scenarios with higher temperature. The results are consistent with what Zhang et al. (2011) findings suggesting that higher temperature results in a higher rate of ammonium-nitrogen removal through the processes of ammonium-nitrogen oxidation induced by the rapid growth of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria during the warm season. Moreover, our results are supported by Paredes et al. (2007), who indicated that for a range between 15 and 25 °C, ammonium oxidizers grow fast reducing the concentration of ammonium.

The high concentration of TP in constructed wetland mesocosms under the current climate scenario indicates a lower percentage of TP removal, which was supposedly triggered by the declining activity of phosphate-accumulating organisms during colder periods (Yan and Xu, 2014). The higher concentration of nutrients in the current climate indicates a weak function of constructed wetlands to consume the internally released nutrients. The other studies in line with our results revealed that lower temperature (mean temperature of 8.9 °C) tended to decrease the performance of constructed wetlands to lower the concentration of NH₄-N and TP (Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2006; Song et al., 2006; Taylor et al., 2011). Moreover, Taylor et al. (2011) stated that COD removal at low temperature would decrease, if the media are unplanted.

The TSS within constructed wetlands did not follow the pattern of other parameters. Some studies indicated that TSS is not strongly associated to temperature or season (Kadlec, 2003; Hijosa-Valsero et al., 2010). The highest TSS in the constructed wetland under RCP 8.5 and the lowest TSS under the current climate scenarios could be attributed to the impact of precipitation. Plants within the constructed wetland mesocosms under the coldest condition have not decayed as such and, as a result, less organic particles have introduced into the outflow the mesocosms. Moreover, this scenario had the lowest amount of precipitation that could be a reason to produce less eroded materials (Dušek et al., 2008).

5. Conclusions and recommendations

The effect of the climate scenario on the water purification function of two different types of wetland (constructed wetland and peatland) was not similar. The results of this study suggest that the coldest climate scenario (current climate) in the constructed wetland is associated with lower water quality. Moreover, the warmest climate scenario (RCP 8.5) is linked to a higher water purification function for the constructed wetlands, but a lower water purification function and a subsequent deterioration of the water quality for the peatlands, even under water level management. However, peatland mesocosms under the other

future climate scenarios with a lower temperature (RCP 2.6 and RCP 4.5) have not been affected significantly, implying that water level management could presumably maintain the peatland water purification function when climate change is not severe.

The different response of constructed wetlands and peatlands to climate change can be due to the fact that the substrate in the constructed wetland and peatland mesocosms was totally different in terms of the organic matter quality and quantity.

The only source of organic matter within the constructed wetlands was the herbaceous perennial plant *Myosotis scorpioides*, which suffered during the first year of the experiment due to lack of nutrient availability. In comparison, the peatland vegetation grew well and organic matter was abundant. The water quality was therefore very different between these two different systems.

At warm conditions, the low organic non-acidic substrate in constructed wetlands could be sufficiently oxygenated (aerobic decomposition) allowing effective oxidation of heterotrophic organic matter. These processes might be limited, if the peatland acidic substrate lacks enough oxygen due to a high microbial respiration at high organic matter media content during warm conditions. Moreover, the utilization of nutrients by plants and the microbial community may readily exceed mineralization at limited nutrient content (as we had in constructed wetland), when the temperature rises, but this might not be the case when the substrate has a high organic matter content such as peat.

In the first year of the experiment, the wetland mesocosms had continuous water availability and they did not experience drought during the warm season or flood during the wet season. Hence, our findings are valid when the water is adequately available for the wetland ecosystem. Ecosystems may respond differently, when they experience extreme events such as drought or flood. Given that the water quality in peatland mesocosms under RCP 8.5 had a tendency to deteriorate over a short period of time, even when the water level was controlled, it is necessary to assess the response of the same system being exposed to extreme events without water level management as well.

It is unlikely that real constructed wetlands with more polluted substrate or subjected to extreme events can function as efficiently as the experimental constructed wetlands, which were only mildly polluted by an external source. Therefore, more studies on constructed treatment wetlands fed by more polluted inflows should be researched.

Our findings imply that water level management may counteract adverse effects of higher temperatures on the water quality of peatland outflows under RCP 2.6 and RCP 4.5, but might not under RCP 8.5. Furthermore, it seems that the quality of the constructed wetland outflow has improved with water level management, under the warmer climate scenario. However, the authors are not sure if the results are due to the water level management as the effect of water level management was not analyzed separately. Therefore, a new design of the experiment allowing a comparison between the managed and the unmanaged system would be recommended to be able to study the effect of water level management in a more accurate way. Environmental managers will benefit from the results of such an experiment, which will reveal the water level thresholds at which the quality of wetland outflows will deteriorate.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by VINNOVA (Swedish government innovation agency), RainSolutions (Water JPI 2018 Joint Call project) and WATERAGRI (European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation action under Grant Agreement Number 858735). The

authors also acknowledge additional funding received by the Division of Water Resources Engineering and the support of many colleagues (including Ronny Berndtsson, Cintia Bertacchi Uvo, Hossein Hashemin and Erik Nilsson) and international visitors.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112459>.

Author statement

Shokoufeh Salimi, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft. Miklas Scholz, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

References

- Akratos, C.S., Tshirintzis, V.A., 2007. Effect of temperature, HRT, vegetation and porous media on removal efficiency of pilot-scale horizontal subsurface flow constructed wetlands. *Ecol. Eng.* 29, 173–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2006.06.013>.
- Bader, C., Müller, M., Schulin, R., Leifeld, J., 2018. Peat decomposability in managed organic soils in relation to land use, organic matter composition and temperature. *Biogeosciences* 15, 703–719. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-15-703-2018>.
- Bayley, S.E., Thormann, M.N., Szumigalski, A.R., 2005. Nitrogen mineralization and decomposition in western boreal bog and fen peat. *Ecoscience* 12, 455–465. <https://doi.org/10.2980/i1195-6860-12-4-455.1>.
- Biasi, C., Rusalimova, O., Meyer, H., Kaiser, C., Wanek, W., Barsukov, P., Junger, H., Richter, A., 2005. Temperature-dependent shift from labile to recalcitrant carbon sources of arctic heterotrophs. *Rapid Commun. Mass Spectrom.* 19, 1401–1408. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rcm.1911>.
- Breeuwer, A., Heijmans, M., Robroek, B.J.M., Limpens, J., Berendse, F., 2008. The effect of increased temperature and nitrogen deposition on decomposition in bogs. *Oikos* 117, 1258–1268. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0030-1299.2008.16518.x>.
- Bridgman, S.D., Pastor, J., Updegraff, K., Malterer, T.J., Johnson, K., Harth, C., Chen, J., 1999. Ecosystem control over temperature and energy flux in northern peatlands. *Ecol. Appl.* 9, 1345–1358. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761\(1999\)009\[1345:ECOTAE\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(1999)009[1345:ECOTAE]2.0.CO;2).
- Bridgman, S.D., Updegraff, K., Pastor, J., 1998. Carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus mineralization in northern wetlands. *Ecology* 79, 1545–1561. [https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658\(1998\)079\[1545:CNAPMI\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658(1998)079[1545:CNAPMI]2.0.CO;2).
- Burkett, V., Kusler, J., 2000. Climate change: potential impacts and interactions IN wetlands OF the united states I. *J. Am. Water Resour. Assoc.* 36. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-1688.2000.tb04270.x>, 313–3.
- Clair, T.A., Ehrman, J.M., Higuchi, K., 1999. Changes in freshwater carbon exports from Canadian terrestrial basins to lakes and estuaries under a 2xCO₂ atmospheric scenario. *Global Biogeochem. Cycles* 13, 1091–1097. <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999GB900055>.
- Davidson, E.A., Janssens, I.A., 2006. Temperature sensitivity of soil carbon decomposition and feedbacks to climate change. *Nature* 440, 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature04514>.
- Dieleman, C.M., Lindo, Z., McLaughlin, J.W., Craig, A.E., Branfireun, B.A., 2016. Climate change effects on peatland decomposition and porewater dissolved organic carbon biogeochemistry. *Biogeochemistry* 128, 385–396. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-016-0214-8>.
- Dušek, J., Píček, T., Čížková, H., 2008. Redox potential dynamics in a horizontal subsurface flow constructed wetland for wastewater treatment: diel, seasonal and spatial fluctuations. *Ecol. Eng.* 34, 223–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2008.08.008>.
- Evans, C.D., Monteith, D.T., Cooper, D.M., 2005. Long-term increases in surface water dissolved organic carbon: observations, possible causes and environmental impacts. *Environ. Pollut.* 137 (1), 55–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2004.12.031>.
- Fenoy, E., Casas, J.J., Díaz-López, M., Rubio, J., Guil-Guerrero, J.L., Moyano-López, F.J., 2016. Temperature and substrate chemistry as major drivers of interregional variability of leaf microbial decomposition and cellulolytic activity in headwater streams. *FEMS Microbiol. Ecol.* 92, fiw169. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fiw169>.
- Freeman, C., Evans, C.D., Monteith, D.T., Reynolds, B., Fenner, N., 2001. Export of organic carbon from peat soils. *Nature* 412, 785–786. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35090628>.
- Gholz, H.L., Wedin, D.A., Smitherman, S.M., Harmon, M.E., Parton, W.J., 2000. Long-term dynamics of pine and hardwood litter in contrasting environments: toward a global model of decomposition. *Global Change Biol.* 6, 751–765. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2486.2000.00349.x>.
- Hardie, S.M.L., Garnett, M.H., Fallick, A.E., Rowland, A.P., Ostle, N.J., Flowers, T.H., 2011. Abiotic drivers and their interactive effect on the flux and carbon isotope (14C and δ13C) composition of peat-respired CO₂. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 43, 2432–2440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2011.08.010>.
- Hartley, I.P., Ineson, P., 2008. Substrate quality and the temperature sensitivity of soil organic matter decomposition. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 40, 1567–1574. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2008.01.007>.
- Hay, L.E., Wilby, R.L., Leavesley, G.H., 2000. A comparison of delta change and downscaled GCM scenarios for three mountainous basins in the United States. *J. Am. Water Resour. Assoc.* 5 (3), 572–597. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-1688.2000.tb04276.x>.
- Henrichs, M., Langergraber, G., Uhl, M., 2007. Modelling of organic matter degradation in constructed wetlands for treatment of combined sewer overflow. *Sci. Total Environ.* 380, 196–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2006.11.044>.
- Hijosa-Valsero, M., Sidrach-Cardona, R., Martín-Villacorta, J., Bécares, E., 2010. Optimization of performance assessment and design characteristics in constructed wetlands for the removal of organic matter. *Chemosphere* 81, 651–657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2010.08.010>.
- Hobbie, S.E., 1996. Temperature and plant species control over litter decomposition in Alaskan tundra. *Ecol.* 66, 503–522. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2963492>.
- Hribljan, J.A., Kane, E.S., Pypker, T.G., Chimner, R.A., 2014. The effect of long-term water table manipulations on dissolved organic carbon dynamics in a poor fen peatland. *J. Geophys. Res.* 119, 577–595. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JG002527>.
- Höll, B.S., Fiedler, S., Jungkunst, H.F., Kalbitz, K., Freibauer, A., Dröser, M., Stahr, K., 2009. Characteristics of dissolved organic matter following 20 years of peatland restoration. *Sci. Total Environ.* 408, 78–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2009.08.046>.
- Kadlec, R.H., 2003. Pond and wetland treatment. *Water Sci. Technol.* 48, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2003.0266>.
- Kadlec, R.H., Reddy, K.R., 2001. Temperature effects in treatment wetlands. *Water Environ. Res.* 73, 543–557. <https://doi.org/10.2175/106143001x139614>.
- Kane, E.S., Mazzoleni, L.R., Kratz, C.J., Hribljan, J.A., Johnson, C.P., Pypker, T.G., Chimner, R., 2014. Peat porewater dissolved organic carbon concentration and lability increase with warming: a field temperature manipulation experiment in a poor-fen. *Biogeochemistry* 119, 161–178. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-014-9955-4>.
- Karczmarczyk, A., Bus, A., Baryła, A., 2016. Filtration curtains for phosphorus harvesting from small water bodies. *Ecol. Eng.* 86, 69–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2015.10.026>.
- Karlsson, J., Byström, P., Ask, J., Ask, P., Persson, L., Jansson, M., 2009. Light limitation of nutrient-poor lake ecosystems. *Nature* 460, 506–509. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08179>.
- Kelvin, K., Tole, M., 2011. The efficacy of a tropical constructed wetland for treating wastewater during the dry season: the Kenyan experience. *Water. Air. Soil Pollut.* 215, 137–143. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-010-0465-2>.
- Koerselman, W., Kerkhoven, M.B. Van, Verhoeven, J.T.A., 1993. Release of inorganic N, P and K in peat soils; effect of temperature, water chemistry and water level. *Biogeochemistry* 20, 63–81. Published by: Springer Stable URL. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1468907> REFERENCES.
- Laiho, R., 2006. Decomposition in peatlands: reconciling seemingly contrasting results on the impacts of lowered water levels 38, 2011–2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2006.02.017>.
- Lane, S.N., Reid, S.C., Tayefi, V., Yu, D., Hardy, R.J., 2007. Interactions between sediment delivery, channel change, climate change and flood risk in a temperate upland environment. *Earth Surf. Process. Landforms* 32, 429–446. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.1404>.
- Limpens, J., Berendse, F., 2003. Growth reduction of *Sphagnum magellanicum* subjected to high nitrogen deposition: the role of amino acid nitrogen concentration. *Oecologia* 135, 339–345. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-003-1224-5>.
- Macrae, M.L., Devito, K.J., Strack, M., Waddington, J.M., 2013. Effect of water table drawdown on peatland nutrient dynamics: implications for climate change. *Biogeochemistry* 112, 661–676. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-012-9730-3>.
- Moore, T.R., Dalva, M., 1997. Methane and carbon dioxide exchange potentials of peat soils in aerobic and anaerobic laboratory incubation. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 29, 1157–1164. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(97\)00037-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(97)00037-0).
- Moore, T.R., Roulet, N.T., Waddington, J.M., 1998. Uncertainty in predicting the effect of climatic change on the carbon cycling of Canadian peatlands. *Climatic Change* 40, 229–245. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005408719297>.
- Munir, T., 2015. Peatland biogeochemistry and plant productivity responses to field-based hydrological and temperature simulations of climate change. <https://doi.org/10.11575/PRISM/27281>.
- Munir, T.M., Khadka, B., Xu, B., Strack, M., 2017. Mineral nitrogen and phosphorus pools affected by water table lowering and warming in a boreal forested peatland. *Ecology* 10, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eco.1893>.
- Mæhlum, T., Jenssen, P.D., 2003. Design and performance of integrated subsurface flow wetlands in a cold climate. In: Mander, Ü., Jenssen, P. (Eds.), *Constructed Wetlands for Wastewater Treatment in Cold Climates*. UK WIT Press, Southampton, pp. 69–86.
- Ouellet-Plamondon, C., Chazarenc, F., Comeau, Y., Brisson, J., 2006. Artificial aeration to increase pollutant removal efficiency of constructed wetlands in cold climate. *Ecol. Eng.* 27, 258–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2006.03.006>.
- Pagano, T., Bida, M., Kenny, J.E., 2014. Trends in levels of allochthonous dissolved organic carbon in natural water: a review of potential mechanisms under a changing climate. *Water (Switzerland)* 6, 2862–2897. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w6102862>.
- Paredes, D., Kuschek, P., Mbwette, T.S.A., Stange, F., Müller, R.A., Köser, H., 2007. New aspects of microbial nitrogen transformations in the context of wastewater treatment - a review. *Eng. Life Sci.* 7, 13–25. <https://doi.org/10.1002/elsc.200620170>.
- Parton, W., Silver, W.L., Burke, I.C., Grassens, L., Harmon, M.E., Currie, W.S., King, J.Y., Adair, E.C., Brandt, L.A., Hart, S.C., Fash, B., 2007. Long-Term Decomposition 5064.
- Pastor, J., Solin, J.B.S.U.K., Harth, C., Weishampel, P., Dewey, B., Solin, J., Bridgman, S. D., Updegraff, K., Harth, C., Weishampel, P., Dewey, B., 2003. Global warming and

- the export of dissolved organic carbon from boreal peatlands. *Oikos* 100, 380–386. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0706.2003.11774.x>.
- Plante, A.F., Conant, R.T., Carlson, J., Greenwood, R., Shulman, J.M., Haddix, M.L., Paul, E.A., 2010. Decomposition temperature sensitivity of isolated soil organic matter fractions. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 42, 1991–1996. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2010.07.022>.
- Preston, M.D., Eimers, M.C., Watmough, S.A., 2011. Effect of moisture and temperature variation on DOC release from a peatland: conflicting results from laboratory, field and historical data analysis. *Sci. Total Environ.* 409, 1235–1242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2010.12.027>.
- Rustad, L.E., Campbell, J.L., Marion, G.M., Norby, R.J., Mitchell, M.J., Hartley, A.E., Cornelissen, J.H.C., Gurevitch, J., Alward, R., Beier, C., Burke, I., Canadell, J., Callaghan, T., Christensen, T.R., Fahnestock, J., Fernandez, I., Harte, J., Hollister, R., John, H., Ineson, P., Johnson, M.G., Jonasson, S., John, L., Linder, S., Lukewille, A., Masters, G., Melillo, J., Mickelsen, A., Neill, C., Olszyk, D.M., Press, M., Pregitzer, K., Robinson, C., Rygielwicz, P.T., Sala, O., Schmidt, I.K., Shaver, G., Thompson, K., Tingey, D.T., Verburg, P., Wall, D., Welker, J., Wright, R., 2001. A meta-analysis of the response of soil respiration, net nitrogen mineralization, and aboveground plant growth to experimental ecosystem warming. *Oecologia* 126, 543–562. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004420000544>.
- Salimi, S., Almutkar, S.A.A.N., Scholz, M., 2021. Impact of climate change on wetland ecosystems: a critical review of experimental wetlands. *J. Environ. Manag.* 286, 112160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112160>.
- Schlesinger, W.H., Bernhardt, E.S., 2013. The global cycles of sulfur and mercury. *Biogeochemistry* 469–486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-385874-0.00013-3>.
- Scholz, M., Hedmark, Å., 2010. Constructed wetlands treating runoff contaminated with nutrients. *Water. Air. Soil Pollut* 205, 323–332. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-009-0076-y>.
- Scholz, M., 2016. *Wetlands for Water Pollution Control*. Elsevier.
- Smith, R.J., Jovan, S., Gray, A.N., McCune, B., 2017. Sensitivity of carbon stores in boreal forest moss mats - effects of vegetation, topography and climate. *Plant Soil* 421, 31–42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-017-3411-x>.
- Sokal, R.R., Rohlf, F.J., 1995. *Biometry*, third ed. WH Freeman and Co., New York.
- Song, Z., Zheng, Z., Li, J., Sun, X., Han, X., Wang, W., Xu, M., 2006. Seasonal and annual performance of a full-scale constructed wetland system for sewage treatment in China. *Ecol. Eng.* 26, 272–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2005.10.008>.
- Taylor, C.R., Hook, P.B., Stein, O.R., Zabinski, C.A., 2011. Seasonal effects of 19 plant species on COD removal in subsurface treatment wetland microcosms. *Ecol. Eng.* 37, 703–710. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2010.05.007>.
- Verhoeven, J.T., Maltby, E., Schmitz, M.B., 1990. Nitrogen and phosphorus mineralization in fens and bogs. *J. Ecol.* 78, 713–726 [https://doi.org/10.1672/0277-5212\(2007\)27\[44:NAPMIT\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1672/0277-5212(2007)27[44:NAPMIT]2.0.CO;2).
- Yan, Y., Xu, J., 2014. Improving winter performance of constructed wetlands for wastewater treatment in northern China: a Review. *Wetlands* 34, 243–253. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13157-013-0444-7>.
- Zak, D., Meyer, N., Cabezas, A., Gelbrecht, J., Mauersberger, R., Tiemeyer, B., Wagner, C., McInnes, R., 2017. Topsoil removal to minimize internal eutrophication in rewetted peatlands and to protect downstream systems against phosphorus pollution: a case study from NE Germany. *Ecol. Eng.* 103, 488–496. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2015.12.030>.
- Zhang, L., Xia, X., Zhao, Y., Xi, B., Yan, Y., Guo, X., Xiong, Y., Zhan, J., 2011. The ammonium nitrogen oxidation process in horizontal subsurface flow constructed wetlands. *Ecol. Eng.* 37, 1614–1619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2011.06.020>.
- Zhou, Q., Zhu, H., Bañuelos, G., Yan, B., Liang, Y., Yu, X., Cheng, X., Chen, L., 2017. Effects of vegetation and temperature on nutrient removal and microbiology in horizontal subsurface flow constructed wetlands for treatment of domestic sewage. *Water. Air. Soil Pollut.* 228, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-017-3280-1>.
- Züst, B., Schönborn, A., 2003. Constructed wetlands for wastewater treatment in cold climates: planted soil filter Schattweid — 13 years' experience. In: Mander, Ü., Jessen, P. (Eds.), *Constructed Wetlands for Wastewater Treatment in Cold Climates*. WIT Press, Southampton, UK, pp. 53–68.